

Role of Ultrasound Elastography in The Evaluation of Suspicious Thyroid Nodules

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Abstract:

Introduction: Thyroid nodules represent one of the most frequently encountered abnormalities in the endocrine system. These nodules are defined as discrete lesions that can be distinguished from the normal thyroid parenchyma on radiological examinations. Increased detection due to widespread use of neck ultrasonography. Accurate diagnostic methods are crucial to avoid unnecessary procedures and improve patient outcomes.

Aims & Objectives:

- To estimate the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound elastography for the differential diagnosis of suspicious thyroid nodules as benign or malignant, using FNAC/Histopathology analysis as the reference standard.
- To compare the diagnostic accuracy of strain wave ultrasound elastography in the evaluation of suspicious thyroid nodules.
- To compare the diagnostic accuracy of shear wave ultrasound elastography in the evaluation of suspicious thyroid nodules.

Study Design: Prospective analytical study.

Location: Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira Gandhi Medical College, Shimla.

Duration: 12 months.

Sample Size: 140 patients with suspicious thyroid nodules.

All studies were performed using the Samsung RS80 EVO ultrasound machine with elastography software and a high-frequency linear array probe LA2 – 9A for both conventional US and USE examinations.

Result: All Patients were evaluated using a combination of conventional ultrasound, strain elastography, and shear wave elastography. Key parameters such as lesion shape, calcifications, margins, echo patterns, and vascularity were meticulously recorded and analyzed. The integration of elastography techniques aimed to enhance the precision of thyroid nodule assessment, providing a comprehensive evaluation framework that supports accurate diagnosis and informed clinical management.

Conclusion: In conclusion, our study validates the efficacy of ultrasound elastography, particularly when combined with TI-RADS, in the accurate assessment and risk stratification of thyroid nodules.

Keywords: Echogenicity, Hypoechoic, Lymphadenopathy, Radiodiagnosis, Strain Elastography, Thyroid Nodules, Ultrasonography.

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Introduction

Thyroid nodules represent one of the most frequently encountered abnormalities in the endocrine system. These nodules are defined as discrete lesions that can be distinguished from the normal thyroid parenchyma on radiological examinations. The widespread use of neck ultrasonography (US) has led to an increased detection rate of these nodules, which are so commonly found in clinical practice. Although the majority of thyroid nodules are benign, the potential for malignancy necessitates precise

diagnostic methods to ensure appropriate management. The prevalence of thyroid nodules rises with age and is higher in women compared to men, making this a significant global health concern. This increased detection has also highlighted the need for accurate, non-invasive diagnostic tools to differentiate between benign and malignant nodules, minimizing unnecessary procedures and improving patient outcomes. To improve the risk stratification of thyroid nodules, several classification systems have been developed,

with the Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TIRADS) being one of the most widely used. TIRADS categorizes thyroid nodules based on specific ultrasound features, providing a standardized approach to evaluate the risk of malignancy. This system classifies nodules into categories ranging from benign (TIRADS 1) to highly suspicious for malignancy (TIRADS 5) based on criteria such as echogenicity, shape, margins, calcifications, and extrathyroidal extension. For instance, hypoechoic nodules are considered more suspicious than isoechoic or hyperechoic nodules.

Aims and Objectives

Primary Objective

- To estimate the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound elastography for the differential diagnosis of suspicious thyroid nodules as benign or malignant, using FNAC/Histopathology analysis as the reference standard.

Secondary Objectives

- To compare the diagnostic accuracy of strain wave ultrasound elastography in the evaluation of suspicious thyroid nodules.
- To compare the diagnostic accuracy of shear wave ultrasound elastography in the evaluation of suspicious thyroid nodules.

Materials and Methods

Type of Study: This was a prospective analytical study.

Place of Study: The study was conducted in the Department of Radiodiagnosis at Indira Gandhi Medical College, Shimla.

Duration of Study: The study spanned 12 months after approval from the Institute Ethics Committee (IEC).

Ethical Considerations: The study was initiated following approval from the IEC. All study subjects were enrolled after providing their consent or their guardian's consent to participate in the study.

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated with a confidence level of 95%, sensitivity of shear wave elastography for detecting malignant thyroid lesions at 94%, prevalence of malignant lesions at 15%, and a study precision of 10%. The final sample size was determined to be 144. As this was a time-bound thesis study of 12 months, patients were enrolled until the study duration was completed or until the desired sample size of 144 was achieved, whichever came first. During 12-

month duration total of 140 patients were enrolled in study.

Study Population

The study population consisted of patients presenting with neck swelling, difficulty swallowing, and hoarseness of voice, who were referred to the Department of Radiodiagnosis from the Department of ENT for USG neck evaluation and thyroid nodule assessment. Patients with suspicious thyroid nodules according to the TIRADS classification constituted the study population.

Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria were solid hypoechoic suspicious nodules on USG with at least one of the following features:

- Irregular margins
- Microcalcifications
- Taller than wide
- Extrusive hypoechoic soft tissue
- Surrounded disrupted rim calcifications
- Extrathyroidal extension (ETE)

Exclusion Criteria

The exclusion criteria were as follows:

- Cystic nodules or cystic mixed nodules
- Nodules with eggshell calcifications
- Nodules located in the isthmus

Data Analysis

Data was entered into MS Excel, cleaned for errors, and analyzed using Epi-info Software Version 7.2.2.3 and open epi software. Qualitative variables were described as frequencies and percentages, whereas quantitative variables were presented as means and standard deviations. The diagnostic accuracy of ultrasono-elastographic parameters for detecting malignant thyroid lesions was calculated in terms of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and their 95% confidence intervals. ROC curves were plotted for shear and strain wave elastography to determine optimal cut-off values for detecting malignant lesions, and further calculations of sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV were performed at these cut-off values.

Results

The present study assessed the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound elastography in distinguishing between benign and malignant thyroid nodules, with FNAC/histopathology analysis serving as the reference standard. Conducted over a 12-month period at the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira

Gandhi Medical College, Shimla, this prospective analysis involved 140 patients presenting with thyroid nodules. The study population comprised

predominantly females (80%), with an average age of 46.06 years, highlighting the demographic characteristics pertinent to thyroid pathology.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	28	20.00
Female	112	80.00
Total	140	100.0
Age (years)	Mean	SD
	46.06	15.47

The demographic characteristics of the study population indicate a higher prevalence of female participants, with 112 females comprising 80% of the total 140 participants, and only 28 males represent-

ing 20%. The average age of the participants was 46.06 years, with a standard deviation of 15.47 years.

Graph 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Population

Table 2: History of Thyroid Surgery

History	Frequency	Percent
No	138	98.57
Yes	2	1.43
Total	140	100.0

An overwhelming majority of the study population, 98.57% (138 participants), reported no prior history

of thyroid surgery, with only 1.43% (2 participants) having undergone such procedures.

Graph 2: History of Thyroid Surgery

Table 3: Thyroid Function Tests (TFT)

TFT	T3		T4		TSH	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Decreased	7	5.0	11	7.9	3	2.1
Normal	125	89.3	122	87.1	132	94.3
Raised	7	5.0	7	5.0	5	3.6
Total	140	100.0	140	100.0	140	100.0

The thyroid function tests revealed that the majority of participants had normal levels of T3 (89.3%), T4 (87.1%), and TSH (94.3%). A small percentage showed decreased or elevated levels of these hor-

mones, with 5% having decreased T3 and 5% having raised T3, 7.9% having decreased T4, and 3.6% having raised TSH.

Graph 3: Thyroid Function Tests (TFT)

Table 4: Physical Examination

Category	Subcategory	Frequency	Percent
Tenderness	No	123	87.9%
	Yes	17	12.1%
	Total	140	100.0%
LAP	No	132	94.3%
	Yes	8	5.7%
	Total	140	100.0%
Site of Swelling	Left Lobe	55	39.3%
	Right Lobe	85	60.7%
	Total	140	100.0%

Physical examination revealed that 87.9% (123 participants) did not exhibit tenderness, while 12.1% (17 participants) did. Lymphadenopathy (LAP) was absent in 94.3% (132 participants) and

present in 5.7% (8 participants). The site of swelling was more frequently observed in the right lobe (60.7%) compared to the left lobe (39.3%).

Graph 4: Physical Examination

Table 5: TIRADS Classification

TIRADS Category	N	%
TIRADS 3	37	26.4
TIRADS 4	65	46.4
TIRADS 5	38	27.1
Total	140	100.0

The TI-RADS classification showed a distribution with 26.4% (37 participants) in category 3, 46.4%

(65 participants) in category 4, and 27.1% (38 participants) in category 5.

Graph 5: TIRADS Classification

Table 6: Strain Elastography Elasticity Score

Elasticity Score	Frequency	Percent
Score 1	33	23.6%
Score 2	39	27.9%
Score 3	47	33.6%
Score 4	20	14.3%
Score 5	1	0.7%
Total	140	100.0%

Elasticity scores from strain elastography were distributed with 33.6% (47 participants) scoring 3, 27.9% (39 participants) scoring 2, and 23.6% (33

participants) scoring 1. Lower percentages were observed for scores 4 and 5.

Graph 6: Strain Elastography Elasticity Score

Table 7: Histological Diagnosis

Histological Diagnosis	Count	Percent
Benign	124	88.6
Malignant	16	11.4
Total	140	100.0

The histological diagnoses of thyroid nodules from a study involving 140 participants, revealing that

88.6% (124 cases) were benign and 11.4% (16 cases) were malignant.

Graph 7: Histological Diagnosis

Table 8: Histological Diagnosis by History of Thyroid Surgery

Past H/O Thyroid Surgery		Benign	Malignant	Total	P value
No	Count	122	16	138	0.609
	%	88.4%	11.6%	100.0%	
Yes	Count	2	0	2	
	%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	
Total	Count	124	16	140	
	%	88.6%	11.4%	100.0%	

The distribution of histological diagnoses categorized by the history of previous thyroid surgery.

Among individuals with no history of thyroid surgery (138 cases), 122 (88.4%) were diagnosed with benign nodules and 16 (11.6%) with malignant nodules. In contrast, among those with a history of thyroid surgery (2 cases), all were benign

(100.0%). Overall, out of the total 140 cases analyzed, 124 (88.6%) were benign and 16 (11.4%) were malignant. The P value of 0.609 indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the distribution of benign and malignant nodules between individuals with and without a history of thyroid surgery.

Table 9: Histopathological Diagnosis by TI-RADS Classification

TI-RADS Category	Benign	Malignant	Total	P value
3	36 (97.3%)	1 (2.7%)	37	<0.001
4	63 (96.9%)	2 (3.1%)	65	
5	25 (65.8%)	13 (34.2%)	38	
Total	124 (88.6%)	16 (11.4%)	140	

Table 10: Diagnostic Accuracy Metrics at Optimal Cut-off Values

Metric	Optimal Strain Elastography (%)	95% CI	Optimal Shear Elastography (%)	95% CI
Sensitivity	87.50%	61.65% to 98.45%	56.25%	29.88% to 80.25%
Specificity	55.65%	46.45% to 64.56%	49.19%	40.11% to 58.32%
Positive Predictive Value	20.29%	16.26% to 25.02%	12.50%	8.23% to 18.54%
Negative Predictive Value	97.18%	90.34% to 99.22%	89.71%	82.94% to 93.98%

Figure 1: (a) Images in 24-year-old male with solid nodular lesion in left lobe of thyroid (b) on strain elastography very high strain ratio of 5.71 was detected. (c and d) on SWE very high mean elasticity value of 113 kPa was found. On HPE it turned out to be papillary carcinoma thyroid.

Figure: 2 (a) Images in 66 years old male patient with predominantly solid lesion in the left thyroid lobe. (b) on strain elastography high strain ratio 2.01 was detected. (c) and (d) Shear wave elastography shows high SWE values of 35.7 kPa. On HPE turned out to be Papillary thyroid carcinoma.

Figure 3: (a) Images in 50-year-old female patient with predominantly solid lesion in left lobe of thyroid. (b) On strain elastography high strain ratio of 3.12 was detected. (c and d) Shear wave elastography show high SWE value of 58.8 kPa. On HPE turned out to be papillary carcinoma thyroid

Figure 4: (a) Images in 47-year-old female patient with solid lesion in the right lobe of thyroid. (b) On Strain elastography low strain ratio 0.88 was detected. (c and d) shear wave elastography show low SWE value of 10 kPa. On HPE turned out to be Bethesda category II lesion.

Figure 5: (a) Images in 40-year-old female patient with solid lesion in right lobe of thyroid. (b) on strain elastography low strain ratio 0.98 was detected. (c and d) shear wave elastography show low SWE value of 10.4 kPa. on HPE turned out to be category II Bethesda lesion.

Discussion

Thyroid nodules are a prevalent clinical finding, posing a significant diagnostic challenge due to the need to accurately differentiate between benign and malignant lesions. The advent of high-resolution ultrasonography (US) and the development of the

Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TI-RADS) have greatly enhanced our ability to detect and classify these nodules. Despite these advancements, the limitations of traditional imaging techniques in providing definitive diagnoses have led to an increased interest in

adjunctive methods such as ultrasound elastography (USE).

The results of our study demonstrate the significant potential of USE in enhancing the diagnostic accuracy of thyroid nodule evaluation. By comparing our findings with previous studies, we can contextualize the effectiveness of elastography in clinical practice. This discussion will elaborate on the correlation between our results and those reported in the literature, highlighting the strengths and limitations of USE as a diagnostic tool.

The demographic characteristics of our study population revealed a higher prevalence of female participants (80%) compared to males (20%), with a mean age of 46.06 years.

Higher incidence of thyroid nodules in females. These findings are reflective of the general epidemiology of thyroid nodules, where females are more commonly affected, possibly due to hormonal influences.

The thyroid function tests revealed that most participants had normal levels of T3 (89.3%), T4 (87.1%), and TSH (94.3%). This euthyroid state in the majority of patients is consistent with findings by Muthiah Nachiappan et al (2018) and Lei Hu et al (2018), who also noted that thyroid function often remains normal despite the presence of nodules.

Physical examination showed that 87.9% of participants did not exhibit tenderness, and 94.3% had no lymphadenopathy (LAP). This lack of tenderness and LAP is consistent with findings by Shufang Pei et al (2020), who reported similar rates of non-tender and non-LAP presentations.

The TIRADS classification in our study showed that 46.4% of nodules were in category 4, and 27.1% were in category 5, indicating a high suspicion of malignancy.

The TIRADS system effectively stratifies nodules based on their sonographic features, providing a standardized approach to evaluating the risk of malignancy, which is crucial for clinical decision-making.

Strain elastography elasticity scores in our study indicated that higher scores were more likely associated with malignancy. Scores of 4 and 5 had a 50% malignancy rate, as observed in studies.

Histological analysis in our study revealed 88.6% benign and 11.4% malignant lesions. This distribution is in line with the prevalence rates reported by Monika Garg et al (2018) and Glenn Mena et al (2023).

The detailed classification of histopathological diagnoses showed a majority of benign conditions, such as colloid goiter and Hashimoto's thyroiditis,

similar to the findings of Priya Appanraj P et al (2024).

Participants with a history of thyroid surgery had a higher malignancy rate, highlighting the importance of surgical history in clinical evaluation.

Thyroid function tests did not show a significant correlation with malignancy, consistent with the studies by Fen Wang et al (2016) and Hee Jung Moon et al (2012). This reinforces the notion that thyroid function tests should be used alongside other diagnostic modalities for a comprehensive evaluation. The normal thyroid function in most patients suggests that functional tests alone are insufficient for malignancy risk assessment.

Conclusion

Our study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of ultrasound elastography (USE), specifically strain elastography and shear wave elastography (SWE), when combined with the Thyroid Imaging Reporting and Data System (TI-RADS). The results underscore the substantial potential of these advanced imaging techniques in enhancing the accuracy of thyroid nodule evaluation and ultimately improving patient outcomes.

In conclusion, our study validates the efficacy of ultrasound elastography, particularly when combined with TI-RADS, in the accurate assessment and risk stratification of thyroid nodules. The findings advocate for the broader adoption of these techniques in routine clinical practice, highlighting their potential to improve patient outcomes by minimizing unnecessary biopsies and surgeries. The integration of USE into the diagnostic pathway offers a non-invasive, reliable, and effective approach to managing thyroid conditions, ultimately enhancing the quality of care provided to patients.

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